

TPACK AND COMPUTER LITERACY AS PREDICTORS OF KNOWLEDGE AND UNDERSTANDING IN PLANE AND SOLID GEOMETRY

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the influence of technological pedagogical content knowledge and computer literacy on knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry among mathematics students in Agusan del Sur. A quantitative predictive-correlational design was utilized in this study to investigate the relationship between the three variables. Purposive sampling was used to choose the respondents in this study. Data used in this study were gathered through adapted questionnaires validated by experts. The statistical tools used were mean, standard deviation, Pearson product-moment correlation, and multiple regression. This study revealed that higher education institution teachers had a very high level of TPACK. Moreover, mathematics students have a high level of computer literacy and a moderately high level of knowledge and understanding of the plane and solid geometry. The relationship between TPACK and knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry was positive and significant. In addition, the relationship between computer literacy and knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry was positive and significant. Results showed that the teachers' TPACK significantly influenced the students' knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry.

Keywords: *Education, TPACK, Computer Literacy, Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry, Predictive Correlation, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is essential in almost every field and is a necessity for people of all ages to be successful in life (Andaya, 2014). Despite mathematics' utility in daily life, several variables impair students' ability to comprehend and apply mathematical concepts. Plane and solid geometry, in particular, is a critical component of mathematics education. Due to its significance, geometric material is assigned to students from elementary to upper secondary school. However, Purwasih et al. (2019) report that, although students have been exposed to geometry material from elementary school, junior high school students frequently struggle with it, particularly when solving plane and solid geometry problems. This result is comparable to Hidayat's (2018) assertion that certain mathematics ideas, particularly geometry, are poorly understood by students. Many students struggle to solve simple problems due to a lack of grasp of pre-requisite ideas. Similarly, low achievement in Geometry thinking at the secondary level may result in a dearth of students who successfully pursue Geometry-related fields at the university level (Wahab et al., 2017).

While school effectiveness and teacher competency affect learning and promote higher levels of accomplishment (Andaya, 2014), secondary students continue to do badly on compulsory solid geometry questions on public examinations (Meng & Idris, 2012). It is also necessary for mathematics teachers, as well as college and university lecturers, to ascertain their students' levels of thinking before starting the geometry course for students and pre-service teachers and to adjust the teaching level to the students' level (Patkin, 2014). Meanwhile, the Indonesian curriculum heavily encourages the use of manipulatives in mathematics education. This was owing to students' limited comprehension of certain mathematics concepts, particularly geometry (Hidayat, 2018). This situation is exacerbated when their teachers do not adequately understand some geometry topics. The same holds for geometry achievement among students in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria's senior secondary schools. Gambari et al. (2014) attribute the challenges and problems encountered by secondary school students in geometry to an insufficient understanding of the rubrics for creating, measuring, and identifying plane shapes from solids. This concerning trend has prompted numerous scholars to investigate the cause(s) of poor mathematics performance among senior secondary school students. Additionally, the study by Pentang et al. (2021) investigated prospective elementary teachers' problem-solving abilities and capabilities (PETs) in the Northern Philippines. It was shown that prospective primary teachers fared poorly on assessments. It demonstrated an insufficient understanding of unit conversion and an inability to answer problems involving perimeter, area, and volume. PETs fared particularly poorly on easy and average items. These indicate PETs' limited capability in measuring the perimeter of a square and converting from inches to feet and determining the area of a rectangle and converting from kilometers to meters. Additionally, they fared poorly on the challenging item. This result demonstrates PET's inability to calculate the volume of a regular prism and the conversion from hectares to square meters. The findings indicated that future educators might be unable to impart measuring competency to their students.

Furthermore, the majority of previous research centered on mathematics in general. Urbina and Polly (2017) focused on how primary school teachers used technology in their classrooms to teach mathematics. Also, Patahuddin et al. (2016) examined the difficulty of technology integration in mathematics classrooms using the TPACK framework. Finally, Young (2017) published a study that presents a complete systematic evaluation and critique of the design and reporting of meta-analytic studies on technology integration in the mathematics classroom. A small number of researchers have focused on Plane and Solid Geometry. As a result, the researcher argues that the study linking teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge and computer literacy to students' knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry is both relevant and timely.

The information gathered during this investigation can be a starting point for school administrators, deans, instructors, and other stakeholders to establish programs to support students' topic learning. Also, The researchers have planned to disseminate the result of this study through a paper presentation during an in-house research forum at the local, regional, national, and even at international levels. Moreover, the publication of this paper could also be another goal for the vast dissemination of the findings.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine if technological pedagogical content knowledge and computer literacy of mathematics students predict knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of the teachers' TPACK in terms of:
 - 1.1 Technological Knowledge;
 - 1.2 Pedagogical Knowledge;
 - 1.3 Content Knowledge;
 - 1.4 Pedagogical Content Knowledge;
 - 1.5 Technological Content Knowledge;
 - 1.6 Technological Pedagogical Knowledge; and
 - 1.7 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge?
2. What is the level of students' computer literacy in terms of:
 - 2.1 Software;
 - 2.2 Hardware;
 - 2.3 Multimedia;
 - 2.4 Network;
 - 2.5 Information ethic; and
 - 2.6 Information security?
3. What is the level of students' knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry in the areas of:
 - 3.1 Triangles and quadrilaterals;
 - 3.2 Circles; and
 - 3.3 Solids?
4. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 4.1 TPACK and knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry; and

4.2 computer literacy and knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry?

5. Do TPACK and computer literacy significantly influence knowledge and understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research design, specifically the Predictive-correlational technique, to investigate the influence of TPACK and computer skills on teachers' knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry. This study design seeks to forecast future results by analyzing the relationships between variables. Further, the respondents of the study were the students from the selected higher educational institutions in the Province of Agusan del Sur. There were 170 respondents taken from the population size of the three big schools through the Raosoft sample calculator. This study used purposive sampling as the researcher selected the respondents according to the inclusion criteria. In addition, data gathering was done through online survey questionnaires through Google Forms after the researcher collected informed consent from the respondents. The procedure is deemed appropriate in the context of the pandemic and following the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) for management of emerging infectious disease resolution no. 38 series of 2020. The data analysis process used Mean and standard deviation to measure the levels of TPACK, computer literacy, and knowledge and comprehension in the plane and solid geometry. Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Regression Analysis were used to predict relationships between independent variables, specifically TPACK and computer literacy, and the dependent variable.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Level of Teachers' TPACK

Teachers' TPACK	Mean	SD	Description
Technological Knowledge	4.11	0.72	High
Pedagogical Knowledge	4.34	0.60	Very High
Content knowledge	4.41	0.71	Very High
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	4.55	0.57	Very High
Technological Content Knowledge	4.24	0.63	Very High
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	4.23	0.68	Very High
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	4.29	0.66	Very High
Overall Mean	4.31	0.56	Very High

Table 2. Level of Computer Literacy of Students

Computer Literacy	Mean	SD	Description
Software	4.41	0.70	Very High
Hardware	3.64	0.89	High
Multimedia	3.90	0.81	High
Network	4.64	0.55	Very High
Information Ethic	4.15	0.80	Very High
Information Security	4.11	0.84	High
Over-all mean	4.14	0.59	High

Table 3. Level of Students' Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry

Plane and Solid Geometry Areas	Mean	SD	Description
Triangles and Quadrilaterals	45.42	18.26	Moderately High
Circles	35.35	16.38	Low
Solids	42.43	17.56	Moderately High
Overall	41.05	14.40	Moderately High

Table 4.1 Significance of the Relationship between TPACK and Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry

	Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry		
TPACK	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Technological Knowledge	0.29	0.00	Significant
Pedagogical Knowledge	0.34	0.00	Significant
Content Knowledge	0.36	0.00	Significant
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.37	0.00	Significant
Technological Content Knowledge	0.31	0.00	Significant
Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	0.25	0.00	Significant
Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	0.20	0.01	Significant

Overall	0.36	0.00	Significant
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Table 4.2. Significance of the Relationship between Computer Literacy and Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry

Computer Literacy	Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry		
	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Software	0.29	0.00	Significant
Hardware	0.22	0.00	Significant
Multimedia	0.20	0.01	Significant
Network	0.33	0.00	Significant
Information Ethic	0.20	0.00	Significant
Information Security	0.29	0.00	Significant
Overall	0.32	0.00	Significant

Table 5. Significance of the Influence of TPACK, and Computer Literacy on the Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry

Variables	Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry			
	β	t	p-value	Remarks
TPACK	0.26	2.65	0.009	Significant
Computer Literacy	0.15	1.56	0.12	Not
Holistic Model				Significant
r^2	0.140			
F	13.64			
p	0.000			

DISCUSSION

It is revealed that the overall mean level of Teachers' TPACK is 4.31 described as very high. It means that the TPACK of teachers is always manifested. It implies that in this 21st-century education, teachers have high strength and expertise in integrating technology in education because they are equipped with the different forms of teachers' knowledge that are required to enable technology integration in the classroom. They can educate effectively using ICT applications appropriate in terms of pedagogy and content. In addition, the overall standard deviation is 0.56 implies a relatively tight clustering around the mean, which is less than one denoting that the respondents have ratings that

are practically almost the same. The very high level of TPACK supports the study of Archambault and Crippen (2009) that was conducted in the United States. The study examined the Teachers reported that their knowledge relative to the TPACK is highest among the domains of pedagogy, content, and pedagogical content, indicating that they, overall, felt very good about their knowledge related to the TPACK framework. The study of Archambault and Crippen (2009) was further agreed upon by Huang (2018) in the study entitled "Assessing Language Teachers' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK): EFL Students' Perspectives". The study also revealed that as perceived by their students, teachers excelled in four components of TPACK such as technological knowledge (TK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), content knowledge (CK), and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK).

On the other hand, the level of computer literacy of students. The overall mean of the computer literacy of students is 4.14 described as high. It means that the computer literacy of students is oftentimes evident. This result implies that students are already equipped with basic computer skills but there are still needs for improvement on their basic computer skills, media-related skills, and web-based skills which they need for the teaching-learning process such as using spreadsheet software, handling computer peripheral devices, multimedia and even the legal processes related to computers. Meanwhile, the overall standard deviation of 0.59 indicates a high dispersion of responses of the students around the mean. The high level of computer literacy among students affirms the findings of SZ et al. (2014) in their study that was undertaken in the Tiruvallur District of Tamil Nadu to understand the digital competency of Arts and Science students which revealed that students are digitally literate. The majority of the students are average in computer literacy level. Only a very few male and female students are not at all confident in using digital resources and tools. It is therefore computers in school laboratories should be updated to improve students' study circumstances and the amount of time they spend at computers during the day and after school. As a result, computer literacy could be improved. Furthermore, similar results were found in the study conducted by Ic and Tutak (2017) on the computer literacy levels of Turkish pupils attending private, district, and provincial schools. It was found that the level of computer literacy was high.

Moreover, the level of knowledge and understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry which was measured by the percent of the correct answer reveals a mean of 41.05, described as moderately high. This means that the knowledge and understanding of students in the subject Plane and Solid Geometry is satisfactory. Thus, students were good at learning the concepts of plane and solid geometry like how to relate points, lines, angles, planes, and shapes. Nevertheless, the result also implies that the students lack the knowledge to apply some principles and properties needed in learning the subject which causes them to fail some items in the test. The standard deviation value of 14.40 is somewhat large denoting that the scores in the knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry tests vary considerably among students. This result clashes with the assertion of Pujawan et al (2020) wherein reality, students still have difficulties in understanding the concepts of geometry. It was stated that students still have difficulties in solving geometry problems and constructing 3D shapes in general. Some different achievement test results in Geometry were enumerated in the study and all give an

implication that the absorption rate of geometry learning was low. As explained by Purnomo and Machromah (2018) in their qualitative study the major difficulty for university students in the solid Geometry learning process is that learning geometry is not easy, and a substantial proportion of pupils have struggled to grasp geometric principles, reasoning, and problem-solving. Geometry learning problems are frequently caused by a lack of understanding which leads to discouragement among students, resulting in low geometry performance.

With regards to the relationship between TPACK, and Knowledge and Understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry has a significant positive relationship with students' knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry with a p-value of 0.00 that is less than 0.05 level of significance (two-tailed). It means that as the level of the TPACK of the teacher increases, the knowledge, and understanding of the plane and solid geometry among the students also significantly increases. The table further revealed that even though the TPACK significantly related to the knowledge and understanding of Plane and Solid Geometry, their relationship is not very strong having a correlation coefficient of 0.36. This result supports the paper of Rakes et al. (2022) which examines how 17 secondary mathematics teachers implemented technology in their classrooms during COVID-19 using the TPACK framework and the TPACK levels rubric. Results indicated that teachers increased their use of effective mathematics teaching practices. However, there was no discernible increase in TPACK. A link between TPACK and mathematics classrooms was not found, implying that there may be a need for a more explicit focus on using technology for mathematical conceptual understanding. The study further pointed out that TPACK was not the direct focus on mathematics learning but was considered an important inquiry because of the national emphasis on integrating technology in mathematics teaching demonstrated by the national education organizations.

Meanwhile, the relationship between Computer Literacy and Knowledge and Understanding of Plane and Solid Geometry is significant, and positive with a p-value of 0.00 which is greater than the alpha set at 0.05. This means that if students' computer literacy level increases their knowledge and understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry also significantly increases. It was also revealed that computer literacy tends to increase in response to knowledge and understanding of Plane and Solid Geometry. However, the relationship between the two variables in this study is weak with a correlation coefficient of 0.32. Novita and Herman (2021) argue that upon studying mathematics like knowledge and understanding in some mathematical fields, so many other factors and concepts need consideration. Other related literacies also need to be studied theoretically and practically. Undeniably, some opinions mention that technology hurts the learning process. However, the use of technology in early mathematics classes, for example, is still being debated, a concern occurs because students during the learning process need a touch of real experience in learning mathematics.

The Multiple Regression analysis results reveal that TPACK significantly influences the knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry among students with a p-value that is lesser at 0.05 level of significance with a positive standardized beta value of 0.26. It means that for every unit increase in the value of the level of TPACK,

there is a corresponding increase of 0.26 in the level of knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry. However, in a singular capacity, the computer literacy of students has no significant influence on the students' knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry with a p-value that is greater than the 0.05 level of significance with a positive standardized beta value of 0.15. It means that there is no significant linear relation between computer literacy and the knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry among the students. Importantly, the combined influence of the two independent variables, TPACK, and computer literacy towards student knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry is significant ($F = 13.64, p < .05$).

Meanwhile, the model explains 14 percent of the variance of knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry was explained by the independent variables explored in this study as indicated by $r^2 = 0.14$. This means that 86 percent of the variance of the knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry can be attributed to other factors aside from TPACK, and computer literacy. The National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) (2000) stated that technology is critical in the teaching and learning of mathematics and that it has an impact on the mathematics taught. Learners can use technology to help them visualize abstract ideas, organize, and analyze data, and focus on decision-making, reflection, reasoning, and problem-solving. Numerous academics acknowledged that the framework of TPACK has provided the knowledge base for the integration of technology and curriculum. Meanwhile, the positive influence of TPACK towards knowledge and understanding in the plane and solid geometry is an affirmation on Mishra & Koehler's (2006) theory of TPACK wherein the TPACK framework has highlighted teacher knowledge as a type of knowledge that is important in the subject of Geometry while incorporating technology. With an increasing focus on technology, teachers need to also learn how to combine technology with content and pedagogy to create an effective learning environment. This further supports the study of Xu et al. (2019) which revealed Information technology can play an important influence on the learning and teaching of solid geometry.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made based on the findings:

1. The college teachers in Agusan del Sur had a very high level of TPACK as perceived by their students. All the indicators under TPACK were revealed to be very high among the college teachers. The level of TPACK of the college teachers in Agusan del Sur was always manifested.
2. The mathematics major students in Agusan del Sur had a high level of computer literacy with network as the highest level. Software-related literacy was also revealed to be very high. While information ethic, information security, multimedia and hardware-related literacies are found to be high among mathematics major students. Furthermore,

computer literacy of the mathematics major students in Agusan del Sur was oftentimes evident.

3. The mathematics major students in Agusan del Sur had a satisfactory level of knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry. Areas in triangles and quadrilaterals together with areas in solids also resulted to a satisfactory level of knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry. Nevertheless, the areas in circles were fairly satisfactory. Thus, students still have difficulty in their knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry especially in the concept of circles

4. TPACK and computer literacy were both associated with knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry of mathematics major students in Agusan del Sur. This implies that as the level of the TPACK of the teachers increased, the knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry of mathematics major students increased. In the same manner, if the level of computer literacy of teachers increased, the knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry of mathematics major students increased.

5. Knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry were significantly influenced by TPACK. This result showed that for every unit increase in the value of the level of TPACK, there was a corresponding increase in the level of knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry. Furthermore, the large variance of the knowledge and understanding of plane and solid geometry of mathematics major students in Agusan del Sur can be attributed to other factors not included in this study.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Since the college teachers in higher education institutions experienced a very high level of TPACK, to sustain this exemplary level of TPACK, school administrator may provide and support them with additional trainings and seminars related to their TPACK.

2. Since mathematics major students possess a high level of computer literacy, to elevate their basic computer skills, the researcher recommends that school administrators may implement up-to-date educational technology and efficient ICT courses and activities regarding the use of common programs such as Excel, and PowerPoint, Photoshop, the legal basis in using computers and others pertinent to the use of all required digital resources and technology which they need for the teaching-learning process.

3. Since the level of knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry of students was moderately high, this knowledge and understanding may be augmented by mathematics teachers through continuing to improve and develop their teaching styles and learning plans that will cater the learning needs of students that might improve their knowledge and understanding in their major subjects like geometry particularly in the area

of circle. Likewise, students may continue to strive in their studies and review some fundamental concepts that is very relevant in mathematics learning.

4. Since teachers' TPACK and students' computer literacy had a significant positive relationship with knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry among mathematics major students in Agusan del Sur, the researcher recommends that school administrator may offer high quality development programs to advance the computer skills among the students particularly in, hardware and multimedia related skills. Concurrently, they may focus their evaluation on the technological, pedagogical and content knowledge among teachers to maintain and sustain their TPACK level.

Since the positive relationship of both TPACK and computer literacy towards knowledge and understanding in Plane and Solid Geometry is not strong, future researchers may study other variables that will link to the knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry or look into other indicators under the present variables in this study that might improve the weak relationships.

5. Since there is a small percent of the variance of the knowledge and understanding in plane and solid geometry of mathematics major students in Agusan del that were attributed to the independent variables covered in this study, future researchers may also pursue other research designs such as mixed methods and path analysis to discover further association of the variables or perhaps indirect effect of the mentioned independent variables in this study towards the dependent variable.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to ethical guidelines set by the UIC Research Committee, focusing on social value, academic problems, and students' knowledge of plane and solid geometry. The research aimed to address these issues and provide valuable information for school administrators and teachers, scholars, and researchers. The findings will be disseminated through research forums at various levels, reaching as many people as possible.

Informed consent forms were secured, providing participants with information about the study's purpose, rights, risks, benefits, safety, privacy, confidentiality protocols, and the researcher's qualifications. Vulnerable respondents, such as those with disabilities, poverty, or marginalization, were considered adult participants. Data was collected online using Google Forms, following health protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force on Infectious Diseases (IATF).

The study generated relevant information that can be useful to public and private school administrators, providing evidence-based information for improving the mathematics curriculum. The researcher valued their participation and prioritized their

welfare. Privacy and confidentiality of information were maintained, and the researcher ensured that personal information was kept private and confidential.

Justice was the sole responsibility of the researcher, and only students enrolled in the subject plane and solid geometry were selected for the study. Results and findings were shared with respondents, and they were given a twenty pesos load allowance as an incentive for their participation.

Transparency was promoted by clearly outlining the study's objectives, time allocation, and any potential impact on the respondents' rights, health, and safety. The study's findings will be used to improve the mathematics curriculum and support students in their learning journey.

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